

THE IMPACT OF MYOGLOBIN LEVELS ON THE COLOR OF CHICKEN SAUSAGE

¹**Dissanayake K.D.K.K.,**

^{1,2}**Rifky A.L.M.,**

¹**Nurmukhamedov K.S.,**

³**Samadiy M.A.**

¹ Tashkent Chemical-Technological Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

² Eastern University, Sri Lanka, Chenkalady, Sri Lanka.

³ University of Pedagogy and Economic, Karshi, Uzbekistan.

kasunkumar86@gmail.com, rifkyalm@esn.ac.lk +998880089066

Abstract: Myoglobin, a protein present in muscle tissues, plays a pivotal role in determining the color of meat products, ranging from red to brown. The interplay between myoglobin and color transformation is a crucial consideration for producers, as consumer perception and acceptability are closely tied to the appearance of meat products.

Freshness of the meat is a key factor influencing myoglobin levels, with fresher meat displaying a more vibrant red color, signifying quality and freshness to consumers. However, as meat undergoes processes like grinding and mixing, myoglobin can be exposed to oxygen, leading to undesirable color changes. Producers can manipulate color through the use of additives like nitrites, which react with myoglobin to maintain a desirable pink hue.

Furthermore, packaging and storage conditions also play a role in color preservation. Techniques such as vacuum packaging and modified atmosphere packaging reduce oxygen exposure, helping to retain the red color. Consumer preferences regarding meat color vary, with some favoring bright red hues as a sign of freshness, while others prefer deeper brown colors for enhanced flavor.

To ensure consistent color in chicken sausages, manufacturers must implement rigorous quality control measures, including monitoring myoglobin levels, adjusting ingredient formulations, and optimizing processing and packaging techniques. Additionally, compliance with regulatory standards governing the use of additives and colorants is essential.

Keywords: Myoglobin, color changes, chicken sausage production, freshness.

Introduction

The impact of myoglobin levels on color changes in chicken sausage production is an important consideration in the food industry, as color plays a crucial role in consumer perception and acceptability of meat products [1,2]. Myoglobin is a protein found in muscle tissues, and its concentration can influence the color of meat products, including chicken sausages [3,4].

In chicken sausage production, the initial myoglobin levels in the meat can impact the color of the sausage. Fresher meat with higher myoglobin levels will have a redder color, signifying freshness to consumers. As meat ages or undergoes processes like grinding and mixing, myoglobin can become exposed to oxygen, leading to color changes [5].

Manufacturers can influence the color of chicken sausages through the addition of ingredients and additives. For instance, nitrites are commonly added to meat products to maintain a desirable pink color [2,3]. These compounds can react with myoglobin to form nitrosomyoglobin, which is responsible for the pink color in cured meats [4,5,6]. Therefore, this review was conducted to analyze the color changes in chicken sausage.

Objectives

To identify the effect of color change in sausages to avoid consumer complaints.

Discussions

Understanding consumer preferences regarding meat color is essential. Some consumers may prefer a bright red color, associating it with freshness, while others may prefer a deeper brown color, which can be indicative of a more matured and flavorful product. Balancing these preferences is a challenge for manufacturers [6,7]. Myoglobin is responsible for the color of meat, ranging from red to brown. When myoglobin is exposed to oxygen, it forms oxymyoglobin, which has a bright red color. Over time, oxymyoglobin can be converted to metmyoglobin, which is brown and less appealing to consumers [4] shown in figure 1 and 2.

Figure 1. color change during oxidation and reduction in meat products [10].

Manufacturers need to implement quality control measures to ensure consistent color in their chicken sausages. This may involve monitoring myoglobin levels,

adjusting ingredient formulations, and optimizing processing and packaging techniques [8,9].

There are regulatory standards in place for the color of meat products. Food safety agencies in different countries may have specific guidelines regarding the use of additives and colorants to achieve and maintain the desired color in meat products [11]. In addition the transportation stress and the distance play a major effect on the color of chicken sausages [12,13].

Figure 2. color change in the fresh and cooked meat products [14]

Packaging and storage conditions can also affect myoglobin levels and color changes in chicken sausages. Vacuum packaging or modified atmosphere packaging can help preserve the red color by reducing oxygen exposure. Proper storage temperature is also crucial to slow down the conversion of oxymyoglobin to metmyoglobin [4].

Conclusion

myoglobin levels in chicken sausages are a critical factor affecting color changes and, consequently, consumer perception. Producers must carefully manage myoglobin levels and consider factors such as freshness, ingredients, packaging, and consumer preferences to deliver products with consistent and appealing colors

REFERENCES

- [1] Flores, M. and Toldrá, F., 2021. Chemistry, safety, and regulatory considerations in the use of nitrite and nitrate from natural origin in meat products-Invited review. Meat Science, 171, p.108272.
- [2] Fletcher DL. Poultry meat quality. World's Poultry Science Journal. 2002 Jun;58(2), pp.131-45.

- [3] Smolander, M., Hurme, E., Latva-Kala, K., Luoma, T., Alakomi, H.L. and Ahvenainen, R., 2002. Myoglobin-based indicators for the evaluation of freshness of unmarinated broiler cuts. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 3(3), pp.279-288.
- [4] Naveena, B.M., Khansole, P.S., Shashi Kumar, M., Krishnaiah, N., Kulkarni, V.V. and Deepak, S.J., 2017. Effect of sous vide processing on physicochemical, ultrastructural, microbial and sensory changes in vacuum packaged chicken sausages. *Food Science and Technology International*, 23(1), pp.75-85.
- [5] Bak, K.H., Bolumar, T., Karlsson, A.H., Lindahl, G. and Orlien, V., 2019. Effect of high pressure treatment on the color of fresh and processed meats: A review. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition*, 59(2), pp.228-252.
- [6] Boeira, C.P., Piovesan, N., Flores, D.C.B., Soquetta, M.B., Lucas, B.N., Heck, R.T., dos Santos Alves, J., Campagnol, P.C.B., Dos Santos, D., Flores, E.M.M. and da Rosa, C.S., 2020. Phytochemical characterization and antimicrobial activity of *Cymbopogon citratus* extract for application as natural antioxidant in fresh sausage. *Food chemistry*, 319, p.126553.
- [7] Rifky, M., Serkaev, K., dilbar, R., and Samadiy, M., 2023. Development of technology to incorporate dehydrated murunga leaf powder in paneer cheese. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 8(2), pp.79-87.
- [8] Hassoun, A., Guðjónsdóttir, M., Prieto, M.A., Garcia-Oliveira, P., Simal-Gandara, J., Marini, F., Di Donato, F., D'Archivio, A.A. and Biancolillo, A., 2020. Application of novel techniques for monitoring quality changes in meat and fish products during traditional processing processes: Reconciling novelty and tradition. *Processes*, 8(8), p.988.
- [9] Kumara, K., Rifky, M. and Samadiy, M., 2023. APPLICATION AND REGULATION OF NITRATE AND NITRITE IN MANUFACTURING OF CHICKEN SAUSAGE. *Theoretical and experimental chemistry and modern problems of chemical technology*, 1(01), pp. 1-3.
- [10] Mancini, R.A. and Hunt, M., 2005. Current research in meat color. *Meat science*, 71(1), pp.100-121.
- [11] Sezgin, A.C. and Ayyıldız, S., 2017. Food additives:colorants. *Science within Food: Up-to-Date Advances on Research and Educational Ideas*, pp.87-94.
- [12] Rifky, A.L.M., 2016. A study to identify the factors affecting the profitability of contract broiler chicken producers in the poultry belt of Sri Lanka. *IRA-International Journal of Applied Sciences*, 5(3), pp.155-160.
- [13] Kumara, K., Rifky, M. and Samadiy, M., 2023. Application and regulation of nitrate and nitrite in manufacturing of chicken sausage. *Theoretical & experimental chemistry and modern problems of chemical technology*, 1(1), pp. 1-3.
- [14] Ramanathan, R., Lusk, J.L., Reuter, R., Mafi, G.G. and VanOverbeke, D.L., 2019. Consumer practices and risk factors that predispose to premature browning in cooked ground beef. *Meat and Muscle Biology*, 3(1).